

Supplementary information

RELEASE-AI: A Lifecycle Framework for AI Development and Disclosure Control in Trusted Research Environments

This document contains detailed supplementary information and annexes for the RELEASE-AI (*Risk Evaluation and Lifecycle Accountability for Secure Egress of Artificial Intelligence*) framework.

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Annex I: Supplementary and detailed information on the RELEASE-AI framework statements.

This annex contains detailed and extra information for all the statements of the RELEASE-AI framework. In short, in a TRE all AI/ML related projects must follow specific guidance in addition to the TRE's standard operating procedures for projects creating and egressing 'non-AI' types of outputs(1–3).

General considerations

- **C1.** TRE operator and Users need specific training on the additional risks introduced by different types of ML, mitigation strategies, and data privacy for AI/ML in general(4–6). The training should be role specific for everyone involved.
 - The TRE must provide the training for the relevant actors in AI/ML projects.
 - TRE staff and researchers need specific training on the additional risks introduced by different types of ML, mitigation strategies, and data privacy for AI/ML in general. Find more guidance here(7).
- **C2.** Disclosure control for AI/ML models requires specialised tools, processes, and expertise. Output checking for some types of models might not be supported or possible. In other cases, it can be complex and require extra resources(8).
 - Some TREs may choose to support only a specific subset of possible AI/ML methods, while others may try to accommodate more widely. This is a local decision to balance risk and resources to manage those risks on behalf of the data controllers.
- **C3.** Computational costs to train a model, and subsequently assess the model for disclosure risk, may be high, depending on the method used, the data volume and its dimensionality.
 - The project team must specify the computational requirements for the project and ensure the TRE can accommodate them.
- **C4.** Releasing multiple models within a project, trained using different data splits, parameters or initialisations (excluding those methods that by design combine several models with only one final output to the user, such as ensemble methods), can

introduce risks such as disclosure via differencing that must be evaluated (8). The type and number of models to be egressed should be planned, discussed, and agreed between the Project Team and the TRE Operators at the proposal stage.

- Researchers may choose to manually divide the dataset and train separate models for different subgroups or cohorts. This is often done to improve model accuracy or reduce bias. When doing this, it's important to check for any overlap between subgroups, as this can increase the risk of re-identification.
- One key risk is *differencing*, where comparing outputs from different sub-models might reveal sensitive information about individuals.
- Many of the differencing risks seen in traditional statistical outputs also apply here. For example:
 - Using different methods to pre-process or aggregate data.
 - Changing the criteria used to select data, which could result in some subgroups having only one or a few individuals.
 - Comparing outputs from slightly different models or datasets, which can unintentionally reveal sensitive differences.

Recommendations by Phase of Project

The inclusion of AI/ML methodologies within a sensitive data project impacts the decision-making by TRE operators and project teams in terms of risk management and mitigation. Although the focus is here is on disclosure control and egress, a breakdown is provided for each of the six phases of a typical research project.

Design phase

- **DS1.** [+] Experts on the data to be analysed, AI privacy, ethicists, AI developers, and data scientists could be consulted or employed throughout the duration of the project (6,9–11).
 - Some datasets may contain duplicated information, which can increase the risk of privacy breaches. In some cases, these duplications are only apparent to experts familiar with the specific data.
 - Real-world datasets can be quite messy, contain inconsistent notations, and the clean-up process might be complex and lengthy.
 - AI/ML experts and data scientists bring valuable expertise in best practices and standards, often making significant contribution to the projects' success.
- **DS2.** [++] The project team should contact the TRE provider to help outlining the feasibility of the project. The project team should consider which AI/ML techniques are appropriate for the project and supported by the TRE. This should include whether the amount of data available is sufficient for AI/ML.
 - This analysis should take into account issues like the size of the cohort, and class imbalance and how these may be mitigated.
 - If not enough data, traditional statistics might make more sense. Applying AI/ML techniques for very small datasets increases significantly the risk of disclosure.
 - When some classes have very few number of instances, there is a risk of class disclosure (class imbalance problem), which must be mitigated.
 - Ensure that the data will be processed in the same manner at inference time as it was done while creating the model.

- **DS3.** [+++] Mitigation measures must be defined, including privacy-enhancing strategies (e.g., Safe Model wrappers, differential privacy(11), addressing class imbalance, and how to implement best practices to prevent data leakage.
 - How they propose to meet certain conditions within the ICO 'AI and Data Protection Toolkit'(13) (or equivalent documentation) such as (but not limited to) avoiding 'model creep', assessing bias within the model.
 - Propose strategies for estimating the performance of the trained models. Some approaches (e.g. cross-validation) have implications for disclosure risk assessment – especially if the model is retrained on the whole dataset *after* the performance has been estimated.
 - The Project Team and TRE Operator must discuss how Disclosure risk assessment is to be jointly conducted, and appropriate mitigation strategies identified. In most cases this will involve running automated assessments, so the project team must provide certain information- such as exact details of train-test splits and code to perform and preprocessing. See companion document ML Risk Assessment agreement(12).
 - Mitigation strategies are more readily defined and implemented at this stage, and responsibilities for their implementation can be identified.
 - Consider if privacy preserving methods or Safe Model wrappers can be applied.
 - Research projects are by their nature fluid regarding what the final output will look like. Uncertainty should be included in the risk mitigation plan and multiple relevant options can be identified. This can be further addressed as the project progresses.
- **DS4.** [+++] The Project Team must specify the number and type of models to be ingressed and egressed (e.g., regression, classification, generative AI) and where the model is proposed to be deployed (such as third party systems and devices including wearables or third party secure environments).
 - The project team must specify required software packages and computation (hardware).
 - The number of models to be ingressed and their type (regression, classification, generative AI, etc.)
 - The type (regression, classification, generative AI, etc.) of models to be egressed,
 - The proposed location of where the model will be stored/deployed after egress. For example, a non-exhaustive list of options with different implications might include: open access internet repository; within secure environment (e.g., NHS Trust); within secure company systems; or embedded within openly available devices.
 - Whether Meta-data and code is to be egressed.
- **DS5.** [++] The Project Team should attempt to quantify the expected benefit of the risk score and the expected cost from disclosure risks on a comparable scale. Decisions on data security processes should be made with consideration of this cost-benefit trade-off, with awareness that, in general, actions to improve data security (e.g. differential privacy, model choice restriction) will impair performance and reduce benefit.

Governance phase

- **G1.** [+++] The Project Team is responsible for the model created and outputs generated. They must align as a 'Safe Person' within the Five Safes Framework(13), they must follow best practices to mitigate bias and prevent harm, such as those

outlined in the SPIRIT-AI(14), CONSORT-AI(15), FUTURE-AI(6) , ICO(16) and DOME(17) guidelines. The exact application of these guidelines must be agreed upon at the proposal stage.

- This includes ensuring the model does not deliberately and disproportionately impact or discriminate against any individual or population group.
- In a TRE context the risk of harm to a sub-group from a trained model might derive from it displaying: (i) relatively lower predictive performance; or (ii) higher risk of vulnerability to privacy attacks.
- Discuss and agree any proposed ingress of AI/ML and process.
- Ensure the proposed deployment system is compatible with the model. If asked before egress stage, need to make sure that all the information provided still apply at the moment of disclosure control.

 - **G2.** [+] The TRE Operator could reserve the right to set aside a portion of the project data extract for disclosure risk assessment(18). In such cases, the Project Team and TRE Users must be informed, and the TRE User must provide the code to process the data and run queries to the model with appropriate documentation. This must be agreed upon in advance and applied only when essential, based on the output check required by the project specifications.

 - **G3.** [+++] Mitigation strategies must be identified and agreed to avoid data breaches on deployment. Different mitigations may be required by one or more actors throughout the project duration. They must be clearly identified and applied accordingly.

- Evaluate all the potential risks and mitigations strategies.
- A model not used as intended could increase the risk of privacy leakage(6). For example, a model trained with hospital data to be deployed in primary settings.
- Deploying a model for use other than it was trained for (and use of data approved) risks directly violating one of the conditions in the ICO's AI risk assessment toolkit(16).

 - **G4.** [+++] The Project Team, TRE operator, and Data Controller must agree on a licence for the output model. The TRE can reserve the right to enforce a preferred licence.

- All relevant Licensing Conditions (for example, around use of software) and Legal Arrangements or Documentation.

Development phase

 - **DEV1.** [+++] The TRE User or Project Team must provide all the information required about any AI/ML model to be ingressed, including type, pre-training details, licence of the pre-trained model and data.

- The Project Team must provide information about any trained AI/ML model to be ingressed, including:
 - The type of ML/AI algorithm.
 - How it was pretrained, including where, and on what datasets (e.g. links to published paper).
 - What checks have been done on the original data licence, model licence limitations and T&C to ensure it can be hosted in the TRE and combined with the new provided dataset.
 - Details of what ingress risk evaluation has been performed.

- **DEV2.** [++] The TRE Operator should perform an ingress risk assessment for any AI/ML pre-trained models, according to TRE operational procedures for ingress. TRE Operator could recognise the need to facilitate fast and simple ingress of small blocks of computer code.
 - Small blocks of code could include up to 10 KB of data. Those few lines are in general easy to memorise and replicate anyway.
 - The ingress should be an easy process and fast process to ensure the developer can spend time where it matters most.
- **DEV3.** [+++] The TRE User must follow best practices for ML and coding(6,9).
 - Model training methodologies which are at risk of over-training are also at risk of being a disclosure risk(19).
- **DEV4.** [++] The TRE User should document the process followed to create the model. This information will be useful or even required for releasing the model. Some processing and engineering of the data can lead to privacy threats, like data-induced leakage, preprocessing or data split-related leakage(20).
 - The particularly the choice of hyperparameters (settings that guide the learning process) - can significantly affect the risk of disclosure.
 - Some TREs might require seeing the code prior to release the model even if the code itself is not egressed.
 - Some TRE users may want to release code as part of the project to be able to run the model as designed.
 - Any subsets of source data retained for disclosure control purposes must not be available to researchers ahead of egress requests.

Evaluation phase

- **E1.** [+] TRE Users could perform benchmarking of the model against the current standards. This (optional) information could be essential in some circumstances for disclosure control to reach a verdict.
- **E2.** [+++] The generated model must comply with all the TRE requirements. The TRE User must provide all agreed documentation and information on how the model was created.
 - The TRE User should provide documentation on how best practice, such as hyperparameter tuning, has been followed to reduce the generalisation error (gap between accuracy on training and tests sets. Published results(19) suggest that generalisation error is highly correlated with increased risk of vulnerability other than membership inference attacks.
- **E3.** [++] TRE Users should use 'sacroml' tool(21), and/or any other tools used by the TRE for disclosure control, for self-evaluation prior to request release.
 - The Researcher and Project team should show how they managed their privacy-utility risks trade-offs. This allows for a smoother egress process.

Disclosure control phase

- **DC1.** [+] Projects could be categorised according to the overall risk of data privacy issues, based on project characteristics, mitigation measures applied, and the likelihood of the model created being attacked. Lower risk projects could have less strict, or even less disclosure controls, whereas high risk projects could need more strict or extra controls, as shown in Table 1. This must be defined by the TRE Operator and communicated with the Project Team.

- In some cases, a project might not need to take a ML model out of the TRE – for example, if the goal is simply to test how well an existing model performs on a new set of data. In these situations, the secure environment (TRE) can offer more flexibility in what types of ML work are allowed. Any results leaving the TRE should be limited to summary information, like accuracy scores or performance tables, which can be reviewed for privacy risks just like other standard outputs. However, if there is a later request to remove the model itself - especially if it has been retrained - this would fall outside the original scope of project approval.
- An evaluation on the safety and trustworthiness of the model host third-party environment could be needed.
- **DC2.** [+++] The TRE User must provide all the information required for the TRE disclosure control process. This may include: documentation, code, benchmarks, etc.
 - Make clear that all the information refers to outputs to be egressed, and not e.g. to a general performance of the classifier type.
 - A good practice would be to collect all this information via the TRE's process for making egress requests.
 - Provide code appropriately separated into files and/or functions/methods as needed for the agreed disclosure control processes. For example, the sacro-ml toolkit is able to run more tests, and hence provide more assurance, if it has specific details of train/test splits, and code provided in a form it can re-use for some attacks. Details are provided in the (22). Other toolkits have similar requirements.
- **DC3.** [+++] The Output Checkers must perform the AI/ML specific disclosure controls required according to the TRE Standard Operating Procedures, and any other checks as agreed for the specific project.
 - TRE will evaluate all the outputs for disclosure control. The level of checks involved may be project related. In general, checks should be taking into account how to evaluate risks posed by the type of model in combination with mitigation strategies and place of model deployment. For example, if deployed in an NHS setting, or to a third party, or wearable device.
 - In general checks include:
 - Check for data embedded within the model.
 - Preprocessing and data engineering (as some practices may lead to privacy leakage. This is project specific(20)).
 - Ensure the test data has not been seen by the model to be egressed.
 - Simulate attacks.
 - Any other checks specific to the risks associated with the model.
 - Use relevant metrics.
 - Governance and licensing checks should be applied, especially if medical application is expected.
- **DC4.** [++] Outputs should be evaluated carefully within the overall context, not only individually. Metadata associated with the project (data, model, processing, engineering, etc.) could potentially increase the risk of disclosure. For example, details of the data distribution could lead to an adversarial attacker to be more successful.

Release phase

- **R1.** [+] A register of projects with details of the type of model, dataset and other project specific information could be beneficial to estimate future project risks for the TRE Operator.
- **R2.** [+++] The TRE must provide all the outputs requested and approved for egress in appropriate means for transfer.
- **R3.** [+] The project team could maintain a model use register (either TRE-specific or via subscription to a national service).
 - The register might include details of the risk assessment, mitigation processes, and the final egress decision.
 - For greater assurance, (and where output-checking software provides) this register *could* contain sufficient levels of information (for example, about dataset sizes and distributions, versions of software used for model training and risk assessment, ...) to fit in with current and nascent standards such as the 'Trustworthy AI Bill of Materials' (or others, as they evolve)
- **R4.** [+] A plan for reviewing and potentially decommissioning the model could be encouraged to have. For example, when the model is out of date, not fit for purpose anymore, or issues detected including data privacy related.

Annex II: Processes for making egress decisions

A companion document is being developed⁽²³⁾ that groups different types of AI models based on the kind of predictions they make. For each group, the document outlines:

- the potential risks associated with the type,
- Methods for assessing how likely those risks are for a specific case, and
- Potential strategies for managing or reducing those risks.

It may be considered natural therefore to view the outputs of the AI disclosure risk assessments as providing a form of '*Risk Likelihood*' score.

Many TREs will be familiar with some form of 'Data Tiering' to describe the '*Risk Severity*' associated with different forms of data, based on the potential *impact* of a disclosure breach of that data.

This suggests it may be appropriate for TREs to develop a Risk Matrix that combines likelihood and severity on different axis to define a 'Risk Level' to help in their decision making.

We note in passing that risk assessment tools may be able to produce evidence that the pre-processing or data modelling has effectively moved the data to a lower severity level. In that case, the output checkers may decide that although the risk likelihood may remain high, the severity, and hence the corresponding 'Risk Level' may be acceptable.

However, whether to adopt this kind of risk-based approach is ultimately a Governance decision. There are also counterarguments that using a Risk Matrix could lead to over-cautious practice which could hinder the release of potential impactful models.

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